

VALIDITY OF MEXICAN MODIFIED CHILDREN'S BRIEF PSYCHIATRIC RATING SCALE (BPRS-C-25)

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Introduction

There is a continuous need in child and adolescent psychiatrist for an easy and fast dimensional clinical evaluation, not only in the emergency room, but also with daily outpatients.

The BPRS-C was developed to evaluate a descriptive profile of symptoms, and it is applicable to an extensive rank of psychiatric disorders in children and adolescents. It has been used in investigations, as diagnostic instrument in patients interviewed for the first time, to evaluate the evolution of the symptoms in outpatients or inpatients, in psychopharmacological trials and in psychiatric general practice.

The BPRS-C 21 item is a worldwide known instrument that has been used in Mexico for several years. The BPRS-C-21 was modified by an expert panel in order to cover some areas of psychopathology not included in the original version. In a first attempt with added 1 item for the evaluation of elimination disorders BPRS-C-22 (AACAP 2003) after that we decided to add 3 new items, hypertimia, alcohol and drugs consumption and sexual, physical or psychological abuse (BPRS-C-25). We also decided to reduce rater's variability answers with only forth options of severity for each item: not present, low, moderate or severe

The BPRS-C-22

During the 2003 investigation we established the construct validity by a factor analyses with Varimax rotation, in 30 interviews. Six factors were obtained, which explain the 72.6 % of the variance. Factor 1 (Conduct), groups 4 items; factor 2, (Psychotic), groups 4 items; factor 3 (Depression), groups 4 items; factor 4 (Elimination) groups 1 items; factor 5 (Organicity) groups 2 items and factor 6 (Confusion) groups 2 item (Table 1). The interrater and test-retest reliability values were $r = 0.824$ and $r = 0.661$ respectively.

Factor Analysis with Varimax Rotation of the BPRS-C-22

Objective:
To establish the construct validity of the BPRS-C 25 items

Table 1

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5	Factor 6
1. Uncooperativeness	0.89	- 0.04	- 0.19	0.09	- 0.05	0.00
2. Hostility	0.79	0.10	0.21	0.09	- 0.07	- 0.21
3. Manipulativeness	0.82	- 0.20	- 0.20	0.27	0.03	- 0.21
4. Depressed Mood	- 0.06	0.14	0.71	- 0.20	0.15	- 0.06
5. Fellings of Inferiority	- 0.34	- 0.03	0.67	0.07	- 0.16	- 0.06
6. Suicidal Ideation	0.04	- 0.14	0.66	0.46	- 0.44	- 0.01
7. Peculiar Fantasies	- 0.17	0.77	- 0.09	0.18	- 0.06	- 0.13
8. Delusions	0.11	0.92	0.11	0.12	0.03	- 0.02
9. Hallucinations	- 0.08	0.75	0.39	- 0.14	0.00	0.10
10. Hyperactivity	0.65	- 0.11	- 0.19	0.40	0.26	0.04
11. Distractibility	0.34	0.03	0.55	0.40	0.32	0.18
12. Speech pressure	0.34	- 0.05	0.27	0.28	- 0.37	0.00
13. Underproductive speech	0.08	0.49	0.03	- 0.10	0.76	- 0.02
14. Emotional Withdrawal	- 0.33	0.08	0.56	- 0.24	0.25	0.11
15 Blunted Affect	- 0.04	0.88	- 0.09	- 0.27	0.09	- 0.06
16. Tension	- 0.55	0.26	0.13	- 0.52	0.13	- 0.04
17. Anxiety	- 0.75	- 0.03	0.33	- 0.14	- 0.21	- 0.01
18. Sleep Difficulties	- 0.01	- 0.03	0.33	- 0.14	- 0.21	0.82
19. Disorientation	- 0.14	- 0.09	- 0.22	0.04	0.04	0.90
20. Speech Deviance	- 0.09	- 0.20	0.14	0.01	0.80	- 0.12
21. Stereotypy	- 0.50	- 0.06	- 0.35	0.12	- 0.09	- 0.23
22. Elimination	0.11	0.08	- 0.06	0.88	- 0.08	- 0.11

Methods

The BPRS-C revised English version was double translated and adapted into Spanish, this version was modified and 4 new items were included. Two board certificated child and adolescents psychiatrist (BCP) interviewed together 10 subjects not included in the analysis, the interrater reliability between the 2 BCP was $r=0.85$ All new patients, that arrived to the "Clínica de Adolescentes" of the "Instituto Nacional de Psiquiatría RFM" in Mexico City, and accepted the participation were interviewed during January to December of 2004. Only 2 members of the team (FP & LP) made the 356 interviews. We used a factorial analysis with varimax rotation for the construct validity

Results

All the 356 interviews were completed and included into the analysis. 133 were females and 223 were males. The mean age was 14.68 years. The school average years were 7.5 Our population showed a great comorbidity with a mean of 2.6 diagnoses and a high social adversity 29.21% (104/356) with some kind of abuse. The factorial analysis gave six dimensions that explained 49.3% of the variance. The denomination we gave to the different factors was: Factor I. Conduct; Factor II. Depression; Factor III. Anxiety; Factor IV. Manic; Factor V. Psychotic and Factor VI. Miscellaneous. Table 2 showed the items included in each factor.

Factor Analysis with Varimax Rotation of the BPRS-C-25

Conclusions

The BPRS-C-25 is an easy and friendly instrument that covers the principal domains in child and adolescent psychopathology. It can be applied after a brief training by the raters. The factor analysis showed areas similar to that of the original version. The abuse item was included in the conduct factor and the alcohol and drug use was included in the depression factor, these results need further investigation.

Bibliography:

De la Peña F: Reliability/Validity of Spanish Children's Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS-C), AACAP 50th Meeting, Miami Beach, Florida, 2003.
Hughes C y cols: A revised anchored version of the BPRS-C for childhood psychiatric disorders, J Child Adolesc Psychopharmacology, 11:77-93, 2001

Table 2

	Factor I	Factor II	Factor III	Factor IV	Factor V	Factor VI
1	0.776	*	*	*	*	*
2	0.741	*	*	*	*	*
3	0.734	*	*	*	*	*
4	*	0.742	*	*	*	*
5	*	0.699	*	*	*	*
6	*	0.716	*	*	*	*
7	*	*	*	*	*	*
8	*	*	*	0.610	*	*
9	*	*	*	0.694	*	*
10	0.623	*	*	*	*	*
11	0.439	*	*	*	*	*
12	*	*	*	0.388	*	*
13	*	*	*	0.630	*	*
14	*	*	*	*	0.719	*
15	*	*	*	*	0.386	*
16	*	*	*	*	0.673	*
17	*	*	0.817	*	*	*
18	*	*	0.775	*	*	*
19	*	0.645	*	*	*	*
20	*	*	*	*	*	0.650
21	*	*	*	*	*	0.589
22	*	*	*	*	*	0.491
23	*	*	*	*	*	0.421
24	*	*	*	*	*	*
25	0.433	*	*	*	*	*